

NUTRACEUTICAL: AS A PREVENTIVE HEALTHCARE**Naveen Kumar Verma*, Prof. Dr. Rohit Mohan**

Department of Pharmacy- Nandlal Prabhu Devi Professional Institute Alapur, Barabanki.

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,

Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,

Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17948820>***Corresponding Author****Naveen Kumar Verma**Department of Pharmacy- Nandlal Prabhu
Devi Professional Institute Alapur,
Barabanki.**How to cite this Article:** Naveen Kumar Verma*, Prof. Dr. Rohit Mohan (2025). Nutraceutical: As A Preventive Healthcare. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 345-353.

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ABSTRACT

Nutraceutical are the compound food material which having medicinal effect on the health of human body. Nutraceutical are also used in prevent and treatment of disease by its therapeutic effect. Nutraceutical are consist of natural food source, dietary supplements, functional foods (probiotics and prebiotics) and bioactive compounds that provide extra health benefit otherthan basic nutrition. Nutraceutical are used as the antioxidant which are food or food based product that help to protect the body from cell damage which is caused by free radicals. Nutraceuticals are also used to remove oxidative stress. Oxidative stress is caused by an excess of oxidation or lack of antioxidant defense. Oxidative stress can damage all the constituents of body (RNA, DNA, Protein). Nutraceutical are effective on disorder related to oxidative stress, allergy, cardiovascular disease, skin disease etc. **Example:** Omega-3-fatty acid, polyphenols, curcumin, vitamins and minerals.

KEYWORDS: Classification of nutraceuticals, role of nutraceutical in many disease, Cardiovascular disease, Cancer, Diabetes, Obesity, Osteoarthritis, Oral illness, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Eye disease, Stress management, Conclusion.

INTRODUCTION

Dr. Stephen De Felice coined the term "nutraceutical" in 1989. It is derived from the phrases "nutrition" and "pharmaceutical." The famous founder of modern medicine, Hippocrates (460-377 BC), articulated the connection between the usage of healthful meals and their therapeutic advantages over 2500 years ago. He said, "Let food be thy medicine, and medicine be thy food." Beyond only being a source of nourishment and sustenance, foods are

meant to provide health benefits. As a result, the idea of "adequate nutrition" is increasingly being supplanted by "optimal nutrition," which consumers believe would improve human health.^[1]

How nutraceuticals are used

Dietary supplements: Products containing concentrated minerals or chemicals, such as omega-3 fatty acids from fish oil, can be taken as powders or capsules to address conditions like heart disease.^[2]

Functional and therapeutic foods are those that can be added to a regular diet and are either meals enhanced with useful nutrients or whole foods with concentrated positive qualities, like garlic or beet capsules.^[3]

Supplemental therapy: Nutraceuticals are often used in combination with conventional medical therapy to improve general health, reduce inflammation, and halt the progression of chronic disorders. Support organ function: By decreasing cholesterol and raising blood pressure, many nutraceuticals can assist treat conditions including cardiovascular disease.^[4]

Examples of diseases managed with nutraceuticals

Advantage of Nutraceutical

- Nutraceutical can support overall health by providing antioxidant, anti-inflammatory compounds, and other beneficial effects.

- Nutraceutical provides nutrition support.
- Nutraceutical perceived as safer, especially when consumed at dietary levels.
- Many nutraceutical are readily available without a prescription.^[5]

Disadvantage of Nutraceutical

- Drug –nutrient interaction.
- Toxicity.
- Digestive problems.^[6]

Classification of Nutraceutical

Nutraceutical are classified on the two basis.

- **Classification of Nutraceutical on the basis of source, functional food and chemical constituents.**

1. According to the Source

A. Nutraceuticals derived from plants

Polyphenols, such as flavonoids and resveratrol Fiber in the diet Carotenoids, such as turmeric and green tea extract.

B. Nutraceuticals derived from animals

Fatty acids with omega-3 Peptides of collagen Probiotics (found in fermented dairy).

C. Nutraceuticals based on microbes

Lactobacillus and Bifidobacterium are probiotics. Lactase is an enzyme.

D. Nutraceuticals based on minerals

Supplements containing calcium, magnesium, and zinc.^[7]

2. Chemical Nature-Based

A. Nutrients

Vitamins A, B, C, D, E, and K Minerals Proteins and amino acids.

B. Phytochemicals or herbals

Alkaloids Flavonoids Terpenoids Glycosides.

C. Fibers in Food

Soluble fibers (psyllium, pectin) Insoluble fibers (cellulose).

D. Enzymes

Bromelain Papain^[7]

- **Classification of Nutraceutical on the basis of mechanism of action**
- **Anti-oxidant activity** – Nutraceutical neutralize free radicals and also reduce the oxidative stress which is responsible for aging and cell damage which cause many diseases.

Example – vitamin C, vitamin E, polyphenols and carotenoids.

- **Anti-inflammatory effect** – Nutraceutical inhibits the pro inflammatory cytokinin and transcription factor (NF- κ B) and inhibit the inflammatory pathway. Nutraceutical inhibit inflammatory enzyme cox-2, phospholipase A2 and lipooxygenase(lox).

Example – curcumin, omega-3-fatty acid reduces the systemic inflammation.

- **Immunomodulation** – Nutraceuticals increase the immune defense and maintain the immune homeostasis.

It regulate the activation of T-cell and also regulate the antibody production.

Example – vitamin-D, zinc, probiotics.

- **Lipid and Glucose Metabolism regulation** – Some nutraceutical lower the cholesterol level and prevent the atherosclerosis.

Example - Plant sterols, niacin improve lipid profile.

- **Gut microbiota modulation** – Nutraceutical modulate the gut microbiota by promoting the growth of beneficial bacteria and inhibit growth of pathogens with the help of prebiotics and probiotics. **Example** – Insulin, lactobacillus strains.^[8]

Nutraceuticals in the Prevention of Many Diseases

Cardiovascular Diseases

Cardiovascular conditions The risk of dying from CVDs may be lowered by nutraceuticals such as flavonoids, flavones, flavonones, quercetin found in onions, cruciferous vegetables, black berries, cherries, berries, apples, and other antioxidant vitamins and minerals. They block the angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) and cyclooxygenase pathway, which cause hypertension.^[9] Flavonoid groups fortify the microscopic capillaries that supply all cells with vital nutrients and oxygen.^[5] Grapes' polyphenols change cellular metabolism and signaling, which lowers the risk of artery disorders. Ginger, a powerful antioxidant and anti-inflammatory, is advised to prevent palpitations and hypertension. Allicin reduces cholesterol and blood pressure. The Omega 3 series is used to treat arrhythmias and has the ability to decrease cholesterol. Supplementing with various lipid-lowering nutraceuticals may help manage CVD.^[10]

Cancer

Cancer Bioactive dietary components high in nutraceuticals have the potential to prevent cancer. Herbal nutraceuticals have anti-carcinogenic and anti-mutagenic qualities. Lycopene and other carotenoids have antioxidant properties that help fight cancer. They reduce oxidative stress and act as an oxygen quencher. Nutraceuticals prevent DNA transcription in cancers and regulate DNA-damaging agents in cells. Ginseng is an anti-inflammatory compound that stops cancer from developing chronic inflammation. Fruits and vegetables that contain chemopreventive ingredients may have anti-mutagenic and anti-carcinogenic properties.^[11] Orange and yellow fruits contain beta carotene, which has anti-cancer properties. Lung and colorectal cancer risks are reduced by cruciferous veggies. Enzymes that aid in the formation of tumors are blocked by them. Garlic's sulfur compounds strengthen the immune system and lessen platelet aggregation and atherosclerosis. Herbal nutraceuticals have been shown in recent studies to have the capacity to modify the metastatic spread of cancer.^[12]

Diabetes

Herbal dietary supplements containing nutraceuticals have proven to offer therapeutic benefit on type 2 diabetes. Soy isoflavones, omega 3 fatty acid lowers mortality and incidence of diabetes, promote insulin sensitivity, reduce glucose tolerance and bring blood sugar normal. Universal antioxidants like lipoic acid and catechins, the spices like fenugreek and cinnamon are used to treat diabetic neuropathy, nephropathy and retinopathy. Magnesium, chromium, calcium, vitamin D promotes insulin sensitivity, improve glycemic control etc. Caffeic acid reduces elevated plasma glucose in insulin resistant patients. Green tea and epicatechin 3 gallate reduces fasting and postprandial glucose and improves insulin resistance. Bitter melon, pomegranates are good for diabetes which regulates metabolism and transports glucose from the blood into cells.^[13]

Obesity

The buildup of extra body fat is the hallmark of the medical disease known as obesity. Nutraceuticals with strong anti-obesity effects include psyllium, capsaicin, and conjugated linoleic acid. Body weight is decreased by herbal nutraceuticals such as chitosan, caffeine, fenugreek, vitamin C, green tea, curcumin, black gram, and bottle guard 29, 30. They help lower LDL and total cholesterol and control food intake by secreting leptin and other cytokines including IL-1 and IL-6.^[14]

Osteoarthritis

All joint tissues are affected by the multifactorial etiology of osteoarthritis, which is caused by a combination of mechanical and metabolic processes that work together to deteriorate cartilage. Joint pain limits physical activity, which leads to an imbalance in energy and weight gain. The complications are treated using nutraceuticals such as chondroitin sulfate, glucosamine, diacerin, banana, ginger, green tea, pomegranate, boswellia, oxaceprol, tipi, willow bark, curcumin, avocado, soybean, and collagen hydrolysate. In addition to their typical role as nutrients, they contain pharmacological characteristics and play a significant role in the control of gene expression. There is strong evidence that nutraceutical antioxidant compounds can alleviate joint degradation, inflammation, and discomfort.^[15]

Supplementing with both chondroitin sulfate and glucosamine may help avoid arthritic discomfort and joint space narrowing. Additionally, applying olive oil improves knee health, physical function, and discomfort, stiffness, and edema. Oats, bran, lignin, psyllium, prebiotics, omega-3 fatty acids milk, and canola oil are examples of functional foods that are highly effective.^[16]

Oral illness

Oral illnesses A new term, odontonutraceuticals, has been identified. Because it regulates various molecular and biochemical targets, it is an example of a pleiotropic phytotherapeutic substance in dentistry. Oral disorders are prevented by these bioactive phytochemicals. It might have a big impact on the complicated and multifaceted oral diseases. Green tea, grapes, and cocoa seed extracts that are high in polyphenols, flavonoids, and proanthocyanidins are examples of odontonutraceuticals. Aloe vera gel relieves oral lichen planus disease patients' pain and repairs mucosal wounds. Additionally, probiotics help prevent periodontitis, gingivitis, dental cavities, halitosis, odor, and other conditions.^[17]

Alzheimer's disease

Alzheimer's Senile dementia is another name for Alzheimer's disease. Antioxidants seem to impede the progression of the illness. Nutraceuticals such as lycopene, beta carotene, The antioxidant properties of curcumin, lutein, and lavender effects to prevent oxidative stress-induced neuronal harm. These substances have the ability to postpone the dementia development 44. Numerous research show that vitamin supplements, such as B12 and folic acid lowers homocysteine levels, preventing illness.^[18]

Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's illness The brain's dopamine-releasing cells are harmed by neurodegeneration in Parkinson's disease. In the world, it is the second most prevalent age-related condition . Plant Parkinson's disease progression was found to be prevented by polyphenols, stilbenes, soybean and other phytoestrogens, vitamins C, D, and E, coenzyme Q10, and unsaturated fatty acids. . Brahmi, a herbal nutraceutical, is a natural brain tonic that helps with migraines, headaches, insomnia, depression, anxiety, brain cell renewal, blood circulation in the brain, enhanced memory performance, and hormone secretion. Additionally, researchers employed the dietary supplement inosine, which is a precursor of irate, to halt the advancement of Parkinson's disease.^[19]

Eye disease

A diet high in nutraceuticals seems to be good for aging. associated macular degeneration. DHA, lutein, green tea, Coenzyme Q10, vitamin E, carotenoids, and flavonoids has antioxidant properties and works well for cataracts and presbyopia. Zeaxanthin is employed in the glaucoma therapy, visual problems. Melatonin Coenzyme Q10, spirullina, and soy isoflavones are also utilized to manage macular degeneration. Ascorbic acid, carotenoids, flavonoids, and tocopherol Pyruvate and caffeine work well for retinitis. pigmentosa . Fruits, vegetables, and rice bran all contain Zeaxanthin and lutein both enhance vision. and lowers the risk of developing cataracts. The necessary fatty acid, folic acid, and omega 3, 6, and 9 in rice Additionally, bran supports eye health.^[20]

Stress Management

Stress poses a hazard to our survival and is an essential component of our psychological makeup. Adaptogens are naturally occurring bioactive substances that aid in preventing cellular damage brought on by stress. They boost an organism's resilience to harmful stimuli in a non-specific way. They work to restore equilibrium and normalize stress and mental well-being. As a result, they progressively improve emotional function, which helps people recover from stressful circumstances. Effective adaptogens that stimulate the synthesis of stress-suppressing heat-shock protein 70 (HSP-70) include ashwagandha, rhodiola, ginseng, and L-theanine. Additionally, they enhance tolerance to environmental stress, balance physiological processes, promote homeostasis, lessen moderate to severe anxiety, enhance sleep, lessen sadness, and enhance secondary memory.^[21]

CONCLUSION

The field of nutraceuticals has a wide range of types and variants. One of the fastest-growing markets in India is the nutraceuticals sector. Customers in the higher and upper middle classes view nutraceuticals as a substitute for prescription medications and only because of their advantageous qualities and lack of adverse effects. Nutraceuticals are attracting a lot of attention from consumers who want to increase their energy, physical stamina, and mental clarity. The nutraceutical industry is concentrating on creating new goods with creative formulas and employing effective marketing to help consumers select the best products.

REFERENCE

1. DeFelice SL. The Nutraceutical Revolution: Fueling a Powerful, New International Market. Como, Italy: Harvard University Advanced Management Program in Biomedical Research and Development, 1989.
2. DeFelice SL. The nutraceutical revolution: Its impact on food industry R&D. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 1995; 6: 59-61.
3. Maddi VS, Aragade PD, Digge VG, Nitalikar MN. Importance of nutraceuticals in health management. *Pharmacognosy Reviews*, 2007; 1(2): 377.
4. Ali A, Ahmad U, Akhtar J, Badruddeen, Khan MM. Engineered nano scale formulation strategies to augment efficiency of nutraceuticals. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 2019; 62: 103554.
5. Fernandes SD, Narayana RC, Narayanan AV. The emergence of India as a blossoming market for nutraceutical supplements: An overview. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 2019; 86: 579-585.
6. Boeing H, Bechthold A, Bub A, Ellinger S, Haller D, Kroke A, et al. Critical review: Vegetables and fruit in the prevention of chronic diseases. *European Journal of Nutrition*, 2012; 51: 637-663. DOI: Watanabe, M.; Risi, R.; Masi, D.; Caputi, A.; Balena, A.; Rossini, G.; Tuccinardi, D.; Mariani, S.; Basciani, S.; Manfrini, S.; et al.
7. Saulnier, D.M.; Spinler, J.; Gibson, G.R.; Versalovic, J. Mechanisms of probiosis and prebiosis: Considerations for enhanced functional foods. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol*, 2009; 20: 135–141.
8. Saeed, M.; Naveed, M.; Arif, M.; Kakar, M.U.; Manzoor, R.; El-Hack, M.A.; Alagawany, M.; Tiwari, R.; Khandia, R.; Munjal, A.; et al. Green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) and l-theanine: Medicinal values and beneficial applications in humans—A comprehensive review. *Biomed. Pharmacother*, 2017; 95: 1260–1275.

9. Yuan, X.J.; Long, Y.; Ji, Z.H.; Gao, J.; Fu, T.; Yan, M.; Zhang, L.; Su, H.X.; Zhang, W.L.; Wen, X.H.; et al. Green tea liquid consumption alters the human intestinal and oral microbiome. *Mol. Nutr. Food Res*, 2018; 62: 1800178. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
10. Bárcena, C.; Valdés-Mas, R.; Mayoral, P.; Garabaya, C.; Durand, S.; Rodríguez, F.; Fernández-García, M.T.; Salazar, N.; Nogacka, A.M.; Garatachea, N.; et al. Healthspan and lifespan extension by fecal microbiota transplantation into progeroid mice. *Nat. Med*, 2019; 25: 1234–1242.
11. Dev R, Kumar S, Singh J, Chauhan B. Potential role of nutraceuticals in present scenerio: A review. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 2011; 1(4): 26-28.
12. Kaur G, Mukundan S, Wani V, Kumar MS. Nutraceuticals in the management and prevention of metabolic syndrome. *Austin Journal of Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 2015; 3: 1-6.
13. Conroy KP, Davidson IM, Warnock M. Pathogenic obesity and nutraceuticals. *The Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 2011; 70(4): 426-438.
14. Wildman REC. Nutraceuticals and functional foods. In: *Wildman Handbook of Nutraceuticals and Functional foods*. New York: CRC press, 2006; 1-9.
15. Sacco SM, Horcajada MN, Offord E. Phytonutrients for bone health during ageing. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 2013; 75(3): 697-707.
16. Akhtar N, Haqqi TM. Current nutraceuticals in the management of osteoarthritis: a review. *Therapeutic Advances in Musculoskeletal Disease*, 2012; 4(3): 181-207.
17. Agarwal S. Leading pharmaceutical consultant. Nutraceuticals and osteoarthritis, 2017; <http://www.dr-sanjay-agrawal.com>
18. Bohlooli S, Jastan M, Nakhostin-Roohi B, Mohammadi S, Baghaei Z. A pilot double-blinded, randomized, clinical trial of topical virgin olive oil versus piroxicam gel in osteoarthritis of the knee. *Journal of Clinical Rheumatology*, 2012; 18(2): 99-101.
19. Ruchi S, Amanjot K, Sourav T, Keerti B, Sujit B. Role of nutraceuticals in health care: A review. *International Journal of Green Pharmacy*, 2017; 11(3): 386-394.
20. Varani EM, Iriti M. Odonto nutraceuticals: pleioyropic photo therapeutic agents for oral health. *Pharmaceuticals*, 2016; 9(1): 10-13.
21. González-Vallinas M, González-Castejón M, Rodríguez-Casado A, Ramírez de Molina A. Dietary phytochemicals in cancer prevention and therapy: a complementary approach with promising perspectives. *Nutrition Review*, 2013; 71(9): 585-599.